

Neutronic Interaction Between Control Drums and its Reactivity Effects in Compact Microreactors

Abuzlf H^{1,2}, Gilad E^{1,2,*}

¹Department of Nuclear Engineering, Ben-Gurion University of the Negev, Beer Sheva, 8410501, Israel;

²Klein Institute for Nuclear Science and Engineering, Ben-Gurion University of the Negev, Beer Sheva, 8410501, Israel

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ABSTRACT

The objective of this work is to investigate the complex neutronic interactions among adjacent rotating control drums in a compact microreactor and to quantify their combined effect on core reactivity and the reactivity worth of drums' configurations. In such compact geometries, spatial coupling through the reflector, local leakage, and flux traps leads to nonlinear and non-intuitive multidrum behavior, motivating a systematic exploration of the high-dimensional control space. To enable this analysis, high-fidelity Monte Carlo simulations were used to generate a dataset of effective multiplication factors over thousands of multidrum angular configurations. A neural-network surrogate model was trained to emulate these results and embedded within a genetic algorithm search framework, allowing for the rapid evaluation of the five-dimensional control space. The results reveal several notable physical behaviors. The reactivity space contains multiple shallow local minima ("reactivity wells") rather than a single global extremum; families of non-trivial configurations exist that achieve better minimum reactivity than the "fully inserted" layout; and small asymmetric perturbations to the nominal all-out configuration can yield measurable positive reactivity. These findings highlight the strong coupling between neighboring drums and demonstrate that drum worth is not a simple function of individual rotation angles but is significantly shaped by geometric proximity and the non-cylindrical heterogeneity of the core.

Keywords: Microreactors, control drums, drums interactions, neural network, genetic algorithm

1. INTRODUCTION

Reactivity control in compact microreactors increasingly relies on rotating control drums embedded in the reflector, providing a mechanically robust and spatially efficient alternative to conventional control rods [1, 2, 3, 4]. In configurations where multiple drums are placed in proximity, their neutronic interactions become strongly coupled. The reactivity worth of a given drum depends not only on its own absorber orientation, but also on the orientations of its neighbors, the local reflector thickness, and the non-cylindrical geometry of the core. These interactions influence neutron leakage, flux redistribution, and local absorption pathways, ultimately shaping the combined reactivity response of the entire drum set. Understanding this multidrum coupling is therefore essential for accurately predicting reactivity behavior, establishing shutdown margins, and identifying control strategies in advanced microreactor concepts.

Despite their importance, the interactions among multiple control drums have received limited systematic examination. Prior studies have typically focused on single-drum worth, non-interacting drums, or on idealized geometries. In contrast, realistic microreactor designs feature non-cylindrical cores with discrete internal structures, compact layouts, and complex spatial inter-drum relations. For example, Price et al. (2022a, b) [2, 5] employed a surrogate model for control drum worths and optimization

*gilade@bgu.ac.il

methods to identify critical drum configurations for the Holo-Quad microreactor, with *two* drums per quadrant [6]. In this paper, a later design is considered, having *five* drums per quadrant [7].

These characteristics lead to a high-dimensional control space with potentially non-intuitive behavior, including multiple local optima or families of nearly equivalent reactivity configurations. Searching this space directly with high-fidelity Monte Carlo (MC) simulations is computationally expensive [8], especially when thousands of multidrum angular combinations must be evaluated.

To overcome these challenges, surrogate modeling techniques, particularly neural networks (NNs), have been successfully used to emulate reactor physics responses at greatly reduced computational cost. Prior studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of NN-based approaches for predicting core parameters [9]. In parallel, genetic algorithms (GAs) have been widely applied to nonlinear and multidimensional optimization problems in nuclear engineering, including fuel loading and core design optimization [10].

In this work, we combine these two approaches to study multidrum interactions in a compact microreactor systematically. High-fidelity MC simulations are first used to train a neural-network surrogate model for predicting the effective multiplication factor as a function of five independent drum angles. The surrogate is then embedded within a GA framework to explore the multidimensional control space efficiently. This methodology enables the identification of non-trivial drum configurations, characterization of reactivity wells and local minima, and a deeper understanding of the physical coupling among adjacent drums.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. Monte Carlo Dataset of the HOLOS-Quad Reactor

A modified version of the HOLOS-Quad microreactor design [6, 7] was selected as the representative test bed due to its compact geometry, peripheral drum layout, and strong potential for multidrum interactions. The reactor consists of five rotating control drums embedded near the reflector region, making it suitable for studying both local and non-local drum-to-drum coupling effects. The core and reflector are not perfectly cylindrical, so the five drums are not geometrically equivalent and exhibit different leakage and reflector coupling, leading to location-dependent drum worth, even before considering interactions with neighboring drums. The quarter-core geometry possesses a 1/8-core (diagonal) symmetry, so any drums' configuration will yield the same reactivity as its mirrored one. Figure 1 shows the simulated quarter-core model, highlighting the reflector, active core, and the B₄C absorber sectors embedded in each drum.

Because multidrum coupling produces complex and potentially nonmonotonic reactivity curves, a dense MC sampling campaign was conducted to generate a sufficiently rich training set. Over 10,000 independent simulations were performed, each corresponding to a unique five-angle drum configuration sampled from the full angular domain (-180° to 180°) with a 10° granularity. For each configuration, the effective multiplication factor was computed and recorded as the response variable. This data set captures smooth global trends and localized nonlinearities arising from adjacent-drum interactions, reflector asymmetries, and variations in neutron leakage patterns.

2.2. Neural Network Surrogate Model

A feed-forward neural network (NN) was constructed to provide a fast, continuous approximation of the MC-predicted reactivity. The NN maps the five-dimensional vector of drum angles to the corresponding k_{eff} , providing an inexpensive substitute for direct MC evaluation during optimization.

The network architecture consisted of five input neurons (one per drum), two hidden layers with Tanh activation functions, and a single output neuron predicting k_{eff} . Training was performed using super-

Figure 1. Quarter-core model showing five control drums (cyan) with B_4C absorber sectors (red). Left: “fully inserted” configuration ($180^\circ, \dots, 180^\circ$). Right: “fully withdrawn” configuration ($0^\circ, \dots, 0^\circ$).

vised learning with backpropagation to minimize the mean squared error (MSE),

$$MSE = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \left(k_{\text{eff}}^{\text{MC}} - k_{\text{eff}}^{\text{NN}} \right)^2, \quad (1)$$

where $k_{\text{eff}}^{\text{MC}}$ is the MC result and $k_{\text{eff}}^{\text{NN}}$ is the NN prediction.

To promote generalization and prevent overfitting, the dataset was divided into 90% training and validation and 10% testing subsets. Early stopping and cross-validation were used, and performance was evaluated using the coefficient of determination R^2 and the root-mean-square error (RMSE). Once validated, this surrogate model served as the computational core of the optimization framework.

2.3. Genetic Algorithm for Exploring the Multidrum Reactivity Landscape

The trained NN was integrated into a GA framework. Each chromosome in the GA population represents a candidate drums configuration, with its fitness evaluated through the NN-predicted k_{eff} . The optimization objectives include minimizing or maximizing k_{eff} .

The GA employed the standard cycle of selection, crossover, and mutation. A population size of 50 and was executed for up to 200 generations. Elitism was applied to preserve the best configuration in each generation, while the remaining offspring were generated through rank-based selection, blend crossover, and Gaussian mutation.

The overall research methodology is illustrated in Fig 2, MC simulations first generate training data relating drums’ angular configurations to k_{eff} values. An NN is trained on this data to serve as a fast surrogate model, enabling the GA to efficiently search for optimal configurations. The final step validates the optimized solutions through MC simulations.

Figure 2. A schematic representation of the methodology flow.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the results of the MC simulations, the NN surrogate validation, and the subsequent exploration of the multidrum reactivity landscape using the GA–NN framework. The results are organized to emphasize the *physical behavior* of the control-drum system, specifically the nonlinear interactions among adjacent drums, the existence of multiple shallow minima and equivalent high-reactivity configurations, and the asymmetric response of clockwise and anticlockwise drum rotation introduced by the core geometry.

3.1. Neural-Network Surrogate Accuracy

Before interpreting the multidrum behavior, the predictive accuracy of the NN surrogate was evaluated against the high-fidelity MC dataset. As shown in Fig 3, the NN reproduces the MC values of k_{eff} with $R^2 > 0.99$ and RMSE below 10^{-4} , meaning surrogate errors are within the MC statistical uncertainty. This high fidelity is essential because it ensures that features discovered later, such as reactivity wells, local minima, and asymmetric drum interactions, are genuine physics phenomena rather than artifacts of the surrogate.

With this validation in place, the surrogate was used to explore the full five-dimensional drum space and identify both trivial and non-trivial reactivity extrema.

Figure 3. Training regression of the neural network surrogate model against MC reference dataset.

3.2. Minimum Reactivity Configurations and the Existence of Shallow Wells

A first objective was to determine whether the trivial “fully inserted” configuration ($180^\circ, \dots, 180^\circ$) corresponds to a unique global minimum of k_{eff} . The GA consistently converged to configurations that oriented the B_4C sectors toward the core, but not precisely in the trivial position. Instead, neighboring drum angles were perturbed by several degrees, yet they still produced the same reactivity within the MC uncertainty. A representative converged configuration was $(-175^\circ, 172^\circ, 174^\circ, 175^\circ, 177^\circ)$. This demonstrates that the minimum of the reactivity landscape is not a *sharp point*, but rather a *shallow multidimensional well*, a region containing multiple configurations with nearly identical minimum reactivity. The GA may converge to any of several near equivalent configurations within MC uncertainty, also due to the symmetric quadrant with respect to the diagonal, enabling mirrored drum angle patterns to yield very similar reactivity. Therefore, we report *representative* converged solutions. Representative GA convergence process is shown in Fig 4 (left), where 30 realizations were performed to obtain an average reactivity and its variance. Also shown is the obtained minimal- k_{eff} drum configuration (right).

The small deviations, typically 3–8° from the (180°, . . . , 180°) position, lower the reactivity slightly beyond the fully aligned case. The reason is the non-cylindrical core geometry, which causes the flux near each drum to depend not only on its own angle but also on the number and arrangement of its neighboring drums. Drums 2–4 have two adjacent neighbors from opposite side, producing stronger local coupling and enhanced absorption when their absorber sectors are slightly rotated relative to one another. In contrast, drums 1 and 5 sit at the geometric edges, and each has only one adjacent drum, resulting in a different optimal offset. The combined effect is that the deepest reactivity minimum arises not at the perfectly symmetric 180° “fully inserted” configuration, but within a narrow region of slightly perturbed angles that better account for the nonuniform drum-to-drum interactions and reflector heterogeneity.

Figure 4. Left: Average $\Delta\rho$ and its variance across generations, illustrating the convergence behavior of the GA process using 30 realizations. Right: The minimal- k_{eff} drums configuration obtained by the GA.

3.3. Existence of Higher Reactivity Configurations Near the Symmetric “Fully Withdrawn” Configuration

A major question explored in this work is whether the typical reference “fully withdrawn” configuration, (0°, 0°, 0°, 0°, 0°), actually yields the global maximum in k_{eff} . Surprisingly, the GA found several nearby configurations with slightly higher reactivity, typically $\Delta\rho \approx 15 - 25$ pcm above the MC-calculated reference $k_{eff} = k_{ref}^{Serpent} = 1.11338$. Representative examples of these high-reactivity drum orientations are summarized in Table I.

These findings demonstrate that the assumption of maximal reactivity at the (0°, . . . , 0°) position does not always hold. Instead, small perturbations in drum orientations may lead to measurable reactivity gains, emphasizing the importance of optimization approaches for characterizing and selecting operational drum layouts in these types of non-symmetrical cores.

3.4. Drum–Drum Coupling and Rotation Effects

To further investigate the physics of control drum interactions, Fig. 5 compares the reactivity evolution $\Delta\rho$ for different drum pairs under opposite and same rotation directions. The left case corresponds to drums 1 and 2, which are direct neighbors, while the right case represents drums 1 and 3, located farther apart. For adjacent drums (1 and 2), the reactivity worth curves depend on the rotating directions of

Table I. Representative control drum configurations (expressed in the range $[-180^\circ, 180^\circ]$ with reactivity $\Delta\rho > +15$ pcm with respect to the reference “fully withdrawn” configuration.

θ_1 [$^\circ$]	θ_2 [$^\circ$]	θ_3 [$^\circ$]	θ_4 [$^\circ$]	θ_5 [$^\circ$]	$k_{\text{eff,NN}}$	$\Delta\rho$ (pcm)	
						NN	Serpent
0	0	0	0	0	1.11338	0	0
-8.2	-11.4	8.5	16.1	-2.0	1.11358	16	13
-7.5	-11.4	10.1	8.2	3.2	1.11368	24	21
-10.8	-3.9	5.6	5.8	2.1	1.11362	19	22
-3.3	-12.1	8.4	6.3	9.3	1.11365	21	17
-7.2	-9.8	8.8	6.7	6.0	1.11369	25	19

the drums. This confirms that adjacent drums show non-trivial (absorber-to-reflector) interaction. For distant drums, 1 and 3, for which no strong interaction is expected, the reactivity worth curves are indeed independent of the rotation direction of either drum.

Figure 5. Effect of adjacent and non-adjacent drum rotation directions on the reactivity worth curves.

3.5. Asymmetry in Rotation Direction

To highlight the importance of the rotation direction, Fig. 6 visualizes the thermal flux and fission density for two representative positions of drum 5 at $\theta_5 = 90^\circ$ and $\theta_5 = 270^\circ$, corresponding respectively to clockwise and counterclockwise rotation directions. The transition from a higher flux concentration near the drum surface at $\theta_5 = 90^\circ$ to a more diffused distribution at $\theta_5 = 270^\circ$ clearly demonstrates the asymmetric neutronic response induced by the reflector-absorber interface.

Figure 6 quantifies this behavior by comparing the reactivity evolution $\Delta\rho$ as a function of the rotation angle for both directions. Although both cases exhibit the same overall trend of decreasing reactivity with rotation, the adjacent reflector causes a measurable deviation between the two curves. This asymmetry highlights that the reactivity response of individual drums is not purely a function of rotation angle but also depends on the rotation direction and local geometric coupling with the surroundings.

Figure 6. Direction-dependent worth of drum 5 arising from local coupling with the surrounding reflector, the fuel, and the adjacent drum. Top row: Serpent tallies of normalized thermal neutron flux (left colorbar) and normalized fission power density (right colorbar) for three drum 5 orientations while all other drums are held at the fully withdrawn at configuration ($\theta_1 = \theta_2 = \theta_3 = \theta_4 = 0^\circ$). Bottom: Reactivity change $\Delta\rho(\theta_5)$ computed relative to k_{ref} for clockwise and counterclockwise rotations.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This study demonstrates the integration of MC simulations, NN surrogate model, and a GA framework for the optimization of control drum configurations in a microreactor inspired by the HOLOS Gen-2+ design. Embedding the NN within the GA enabled efficient exploration of the five-dimensional control space, reducing the computational cost compared to direct MC evaluations.

The following key physics conclusions emerge. First, the minimum-reactivity region forms a shallow multidimensional well around $(180^\circ, \dots, 180^\circ)$, not a single point. Second, slight asymmetric rotations can yield higher reactivity than the symmetric “fully withdrawn” configuration $(0^\circ, \dots, 0^\circ)$. Third, adjacent drums exhibit strong nonlinear coupling, whereas distant drums interact more weakly. Fourth, the reactor’s non-cylindrical core geometry introduces direction-dependent reactivity responses. Finally, the multidrum concept contains multiple equivalent optima, both at maxima and minima.

These findings emphasize that reactivity control in compact microreactors cannot be understood by

treating drums independently or by relying solely on symmetric layouts. The interplay between geometry, absorber position, and drum proximity generates a rich, multidimensional reactivity behavior requiring systematic, multidimensional analysis.

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